

THE ETHICS OF USING AI IN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. This paper highlights the importance of the ethics of using AI at universities. Nowadays AI in universities presents both promising advancements and ethical difficulties related to fairness, privacy, and the risk of biases especially in decision making processes, however, AI offers opportunities to improve academic services, from individualized learning to enhanced administrative efficiency. As we know that AI developing day by day so, universities must address these challenges by establishing clear ethical guidelines for AI applications to ensure that technology serves the mission of higher education equitably. In addition to this universities itself would not address these issues because if students use AI unconsciously these problems take a long time to solve that is why universities should try to make students know how to use it consciously.

Keywords: ethics of ai, data and privacy, ai transparency, ai and decision-making, ai and student privacy.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola universitetlarda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish etikasining muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Bugungi kunda oliy o'quv yurtlarida sun'iy intellekt istiqbolli yutuqlar bilan bir qatorda adolat, maxfiylik va ayniqsa qaror qabul qilish jarayonlarida yuzaga keladigan noxolislik xavfi kabi muammolarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Biroq, sun'iy intellekt individual ta'limdan tortib ma'muriy samaradorlikni oshirishgacha bo'lgan akademik xizmatlarni takomillashtirish imkoniyatlarini ham taqdim etadi. Sun'iy intellekt kundan-kunga rivojlanib borayotganini inobatga olib, universitetlar ushbu muammolarni hal qilish uchun texnologiyalar oliy ta'lim vazifasiga adolatli xizmat qilishini ta'minlaydigan aniq axloqiy ko'rsatmalarni ishlab chiqishlari zarur. Shuningdek, universitetlarning o'zlari bu masalalarni hal qila olmaydilar, chunki agar talabalar sun'iy intellektdan ongsiz ravishda foydalansalar, bu muammolarni bartaraf etish uzoq vaqt talab qiladi. Shu sababli, universitetlar talabalarga sun'iy intellektdan ongli ravishda foydalanishni o'rgatishga harakat qilishlari kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt etikasi, ma'lumotlar va maxfiylik, sun'iy intellekt shaffofligi, sun'iy intellekt va qaror qabul qilish, sun'iy intellekt va talabalar maxfiyligi.

Аннотация. В данной статье подчеркивается важность этики использования искусственного интеллекта в университетах. В настоящее время искусственный интеллект в университетах представляет собой как многообещающие достижения, так и этические трудности, связанные со справедливостью, конфиденциальностью и риском предвзятости, особенно в процессах принятия решений, однако искусственный интеллект предлагает возможности для улучшения академических услуг, от индивидуального обучения до повышения административной эффективности. Как мы знаем, искусственный интеллект развивается с каждым днем, поэтому университеты должны решать эти проблемы, устанавливая четкие этические принципы для применения искусственного интеллекта, чтобы гарантировать, что технология служит миссии высшего образования на справедливой основе. Кроме того, сами университеты не смогут решить эти проблемы, потому что если студенты используют искусственный интеллект неосознанно, то решение этих проблем займет много времени, поэтому

университеты должны стараться, чтобы студенты знали, как использовать его осознанно.

Ключевые слова: *этика искусственного интеллекта, данные и конфиденциальность, прозрачность искусственного интеллекта, искусственный интеллект и принятие решений, искусственный интеллект и частная жизнь студентов.*

Artificial intelligence (AI) upends the world of universities, augmenting learning, aiding instructors, and automating administrative work. This rapid adoption, however, brings with it its own ethical challenges that, unless promptly mitigated, may be at odds with the nature of higher education. For example, the personal data, which is a constituent of AI systems, may pose a threat to student and staff privacy and are at risk of being misused if not managed through transparency.

Another important ethical question to answer is algorithmic fairness. Due to the nature of AI, it may end up duplicating the biases contained in historical data, resulting in unbalanced outcomes (admissions, grades, recruitment, etc.). Such potential for bias may extend social inequities further away from just limited access to resources, which reinforces the importance of creating effective guidelines for ethical use of AI at universities (Springer, 2023).

AI-driven decisions must be transparent but openness about roles for AI in these decisions will help build trust among students, faculty, and staff. An ethical use of AI requires more from universities than just meeting the technical functionality of these systems in a responsible way; it requires bringing these AI applications in line with the fundamental social justice, ethical, and humanistic principles of the university itself (Siau & Wang, 2020). Universities providing an ethical application of AI will create better educational experiences and support a culture of responsible AI development focused on individual's rights and equal opportunity AI Use in Universities especially on data privacy the most significant ethical issue. Powerful AI platforms — especially those with learning analytics and personalized education applications — are highly data-dependent, demanding massive amounts of student information, including academic and demographic details (Slade & Prinsloo, 2013). Although this data has the potential to bring about educational improvements, universities have a duty to safeguard it. To do so would require taking informed consent from students, being transparent about data collection and ensuring high-level security protections against breaches (Zimmerman et al., 2021). One more is that it might endanger privacy (Williamson, 2017) because AI systems track learning behaviors to personalize instruction Exponential recommendations to follow frameworks such as that by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU because it outlines principles in protecting privacy of ones data by AI applications thus allowing universities knowledge on the limitations available towards student rightsness protection (European Union, 2016).

Currently, AI Models are trained through large datasets that hold existing biases from the society, which can later yield discriminatory results if poorly handled. Examples include AI-based admissions systems or learning management systems that may discriminate in favor of some groups over others by race, gender or socioeconomic status (Noble 2018).

An analysis of artificial intelligence algorithms applied in U.S. education indicated bias reinforcement, specifically when data sets assessing certain characteristics are homogenous (O'Neil, 2016). Universities should be mindful of the algorithms they employ and how fair, transparent, and representative that use is. To make sure that we are using AI ethically, we need

to continuously monitor for bias (such as through regular audits), use diverse teams in model building and minimizing unintended consequences with each new generation of models.

Artificial intelligence is reshaping the role of educators at universities, from easing faculty workloads through automated grading to virtual teaching assistants. While this enables educators to address more sophisticated and complex tasks, including advanced questions of ethical practice as Williamson & Eynon (2020) suggests, it threatens to dehumanize the learning experience. Even though a lot of paperwork might get reduced with AI, faculties still play a significant role in the overall development of an individual and guide them to do their best. With the unique complexities in learning environments that necessitate empathy and adaptability, research indicates that human teachers offer necessary value add (Luckin et al., 2016). We need to use AI to supplement human intervention—not obliterate it—which is exactly why universities need to employ AI. Preparing our faculty to utilize AI with proficiency can bring a balance into the classroom that will require that teachers be present with these tools while still sustaining the teacher-student relationship.

Ultimately, ethical aspects of AI usage in universities is an issue of complexity that needs to weigh the ability of universities to incorporate technology that students might want to introduce to be a welcoming environment, while also ensuring that students' rights, privacy, and academic integrity are preserved. As the capabilities of AI advance and evolve, universities must stay alert — creating clearer policies and recommendations about its use for the near future. Balancing this we should ensure the protection of data privacy, academic integrity while minimizing bias, and the role of human teachers everywhere, and accessibility. AI will only become useful learning enhancement technologies when universities respond pro-actively to these ethical challenges and, in so doing, can be fair to students while preserving the integrity-bound commitment to academic mission.

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